

→ [https://www.academia.edu/54428725/How to Create a MIMS](https://www.academia.edu/54428725/How_to_Create_a_MIMS)¹

MESS 0008

MIMS 2.51: Induction (or intuitive) MIMS Creation vs. Deductive (reductive or empirical) methods

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ABSTRACT

A membrane is defined as a thin, pliable sheet forming a barrier or lining; in the case of a MIMS it is not necessarily so think physically. In fact it might be quite large, or take up no space at all, but it does provide a barrier, through which we hope to induce a form of unseen osmosis from the ‘spiritual’ (psyche related, or desire, perhaps religious) to the material (physical world or Universe). In the past MIMS was discussed in terms of science, invention, technology, mysticism, God, and of course pro-humanist philosophies which induce good results. There is some question though, as to the formation of “good” or productive MIMS versus poor ones, or ones which become anti-MIMS. Perhaps there is some role to play in comparison of deductive or empirical formation of a MIMS vs. inductive or intuitive, in terms of outcome quality, potency, efficiency, or productive quantity/rapidity. Perhaps the successes of the MESSy standard thus far indicate powerful needs for using *impetus* as a measure of when and what to create a MIMS by. It isn’t clear, and thus a test proposal is made for the 2.5X series.

Keywords: MIMS- deduction - reduction - induction -empiricism - logic - hypothesis - results

¹ Perhaps this is MESS 0000, reviewing it.

MIMS 2+ reviewed - the hypothetical method

In MIMS 2+, the author proposed six hypotheses², which were shortly followed up with hypotheses on War & Government³. The first six hypotheses had to do with direct observation, surrounding science and empiricism, futurization and history, as well as the mystical (being it is tied to some of the most creative scientists in history). These were used to make a proposal on “how to create a MIMS.”

However, there may in fact be other ways. In short, “Necessity is the mother of invention.” The author acknowledges, for example, that the MESSy standard in paper #1 was built suddenly, out of intuitive, representing a half-inductive approach⁴. The other half of induction is that as one acts, more information self-arises, which is itself almost mimsical. It isn’t completely, because it doesn’t come completely from mankind, but some unknown source, presuming the reductionist view of the mind is wrong, as was discussed in MIMS 4.31-4.36.⁵

So what is the “right way” to create a MIMS? To observe nature, human history, economics, and business, and *deduce* the keys to achieving health and happiness from a Divine or pseudo-divine “source”? Or can it (should it) be inductive? Is there, for example, an *enthusiastic* pathway - literally the “god within” - which opens up newness, freshness, and helps one to attain mastery of life’s situations, resources, forces, etc.? From the previous paper we see:

EPEMC :: Philosophy

Steps in Composing a MIMS

1. Identify a need.
2. Translate into a desire.
3. Align the need with the desire, or the desire with the need.
4. Visualize a solution set (hypotheses).
 - a. More ideas is better than few.
 - b. Can include futurism concepts.
 - c. Measurable goals exceed immeasurable ones.
5. Construct a framework (experiment).
 - a. Include the potentially infinite within a finite construct.
 - b. Concentrate upon organizational apparatus.
6. Devote resources.
7. Focus upon the flux (timing) and the potentiality of success.
 - a. See the probability increasing.
8. Measure results.
 - a. Accept unexplained consequences either with humility or attention/interest.
9. Repeat favorable outcomes.

² https://www.academia.edu/50804855/MIMS_2_Applications_discussions

³

https://www.academia.edu/51641990/MIMS_2_7_8_War_and_Government_The_Rise_and_Fall_of_US_Military_Dominance_from_an_Art_of_War_perspective_and_MIMS_Analysis_as_well_as_a_short_discussion_of_the_history_of_failures_of_government_programs_from_antiquity_through_the_Great_Enlightenment

⁴ https://www.academia.edu/87222389/MIMS_1_04_1_05_MESS0001

⁵ https://www.academia.edu/87140767/MIMS_4_31_4_36_The_Storage_of_Karma_and_Junk_DNA

In some ways we can already identify inductive applications, or intuitive openings (where heart, or “gut instinct” can come into play):

1. We can intuitively know a need, or *feel* a need, and emotions are not merely psychic, or neurochemical, they are tied to the spiritual, potentially on a soul level. Either way, one can “know” inside oneself before cognizing in the deductive mind, let alone through reductionism.
2. Desire is almost always intuitive at any rate; but a sudden flash of insight - as interesting as it is - is only exceeded by the **sudden yearning** to make it real. The urge to act, the *impetus*⁶, sometimes is so compelling that we can’t help ourselves, even when we “know we should/n’t”. Kind of wild.
3. Creating praxis⁷ when “following your heart” is almost always a matter of trusting yourself - your Self? - and acting without hesitation. No time for formulating hypotheses, or sometimes even taking measurements.
4. Visualization is one of the most ancient methods of mimsical or inductive reasoning. Made most famous, modernly, by Nikola Tesla’s A/C transformer.
5. While inductive methods don’t leave time for experiments, or the scientific method, it does provide opportunities to continue item four through vision boards, brainstorming, etc.
6. Devoting resources,... well instead of budgeting we tend to see that resources appear, as if by God or by magik; and by not hesitating, one has near instant positive traction, followed almost universally by a) pitfalls b) stumbling blocks, c) challenges, d) evil characters who want to steal your thunder, and e) the desire to give up too easily (paper walls).
7. Here in inductive mimsy we see the “power of positive thinking” and “the secret” and “faith” come deeply, and anti-scientifically (in terms of many means), into play. Sometimes, there isn’t even time to analyze what has happened, but merely to act.
8. Measuring results is almost always - to some degree or another - a matter not of data or science, but feeling, emotion, or pleasure (about the goals and results, vs. unhappiness and frustration). That doesn’t make it less useful, it only means there has to be a numericalization (ORDAINED) approach to understanding the objective truth about good or bad, right or wrong, Good vs. Evil, of an act, object, project, or relationship, etc. After all, mimsical analysis requires a positive outcome.
9. Sometimes people in inductive positive feedback loops repeat so often, and so quickly, they don’t see when the MIMS becomes an anti-MIMS. Take cocaine/Coca-cola for example, or alcohol. These are chemical objects which had good results, much like speed, marijuana, or LSD, do. But in repeated use and abuse, we know clearly the outcome: disease of the Qi Ji or body, mind, and spirit wagon. Furthermore non-chemical mims can do the same thing. Examples include video games, sexual play, reading fantasy novels, martial arts, firearms collections, making “beaucoup money”, family outings, and myriad other things.
 - a. Therefore we add the cautions not only that the Bible has about the heart⁸, and the conscience⁹, but that one must exercise the intuition to help one intuitively know when something needs to be curtailed, altered, or stopped... to remain mimsy and not anti-mimsy.

⁶ Meaning: “rapid movement, rush;” <https://www.etymonline.com/word/impetus>

⁷ <https://www.yourdictionary.com/praxis>

⁸ <https://www.pursuegod.org/dont-just-follow-your-heart/>

⁹ <https://bible.knowing-jesus.com/topics/Conscience>

Test Proposal

The author makes no claim this way or that about which is the more powerful means for creating a MIMS. But it is obvious, from the rate of MESSy papers being released, that when the time is right for something, it can release tremendous amounts of energy long held back. In such a case, if the MESS standard is acting as a MIMS, and it is thus productive despite being inductive and intuitive - a response to a need - then how many other MIMS exist that we rely upon, which are thus? In fact, maybe they often exceed the originals. There's the famous list of accidental inventions and discoveries¹⁰... but perhaps it happens all day long. It seems to the author that the most profound MIMS will still be planned, presearched, and pre-engineered, to produce the best results when finally designed and built. But the author proposes a simple data test to check and see, utilizing 6 to 10 random people who do not interact with one another about the issue, and compare the results of their new MIMS creations. Conclusions will be reserved for later works.

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¹⁰ <https://bestlifeonline.com/accidental-inventions/>